

**THE EFFECTIVENESS OF AUDIO-VIDEO INITIATED PRESENTATION (AVIP)
INNOVATION IN RELATION TO READING PERFORMANCE OF PUPILS:
BASIS FOR ENHANCEMENT**

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The Effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation in Relation to Reading Performance of Pupils: Basis for Enhancement

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Abstract

This study entitled “The Effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation in Relation to Reading Performance of Pupils: Basis for Enhancement”, determined the impact of technological reading innovation on the reading performance of primary pupils. It made use of a descriptive-correlational research design focused on describing the profile of primary-grade pupils according to age, sex, grade level, family income, and parents’ educational attainment. Data were gathered through a researcher-made reading innovation tool. Findings revealed that most respondents were 7 years old, female, parents attained high school level, and family income below PhP 5,000. The level of effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation is high. The level of reading performance of primary-grade pupils is grade-ready. There was no significant difference in the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation according to age, grade-level and parents’ educational attainment. However, there was a significant difference in the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation in terms of sex and family income. There is a significant relationship between the level of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation and the reading performance of primary-grade pupils.

Keywords: *Audio-Visual Initiated Presentation (AVIP), reading performance, technological reading*

Introduction

Teaching reading forms a pivotal part of a child’s learning, helping them to form communication skills that will be used throughout life. In the early years of primary school, it is important to recognize that children learn in a range of different ways too. As a result, teachers often employ practical reading innovations and numerous methods to keep them engaged. Employing these innovations often makes teaching reading easier and more interesting for children.

According to 2018’s PISA, Philippines ranked last place for reading out of a total group number that included about four times as many countries. Gatchalin (D.,2023) insists on how government leaders must help to reinforce this foundation among students and youths.

To strengthen the goal of teaching reading, technological innovation is a supreme undertaking. Innovation in education means solving a real problem in a new, simple way that promotes fair and equitable learning (UNICEF, 2022). The implementation of innovative teaching methods in reading must be preceded by awareness of preferred practices, their implementation in teaching, and their effectiveness (Aslan et al., 2018). The utilization of audio-visual aids in the classroom is essential. These tools, used to enhance and expedite the teaching-learning process, can aid in solving illiteracy as one of the biggest societal problems of the time. Millions of children and adolescents struggle or never learn to read.

Teaching pupils how to read has always been difficult for teachers because they find it hard to read the words to the pupils and repeat them repeatedly if they cannot pronounce the words correctly. Using this method would always render the teachers physically tough at the end of each day. Being in this arduous situation was always discouraging on the part of the teachers whose ardent desire was simply to help the pupils achieve proficiency in reading.

Pondering how to mitigate the situation, the researcher thought of designing a reading innovation that would not just help the pupils acquire and develop their reading skills by conducting reading activities. It is in this context that Audio-Visual Initiated Presentations (AVIP) were created and utilized by the teachers in conducting reading exercises with their pupils. The researcher desired to find out how effective this technological reading innovation is and how it can relate to the academic performance of primary pupils.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the effectiveness of the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation on the reading performance of primary pupils of Sagasa Elementary School, District III-B, Division of Bago City, for the school year 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. grade level;
 - 1.4. parents’ educational attainment; and
 - 1.5. family income?
2. What is the effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) as a reading innovation in helping the pupils in:

- 2.1. letter sounding;
- 2.2. letter recognition; and
- 2.3. word formation?
3. What is the reading performance of pupils when taken as a whole?
4. Is there a significant difference in the AVIP-assisted reading innovation when pupils are grouped according to their profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation and the reading performance of pupils?
6. Based on the results of the study, what enhancement activity may be formulated?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used for this study was descriptive-correlational. The descriptive part focused on describing the profile of primary school pupils, such as grade level, family income, and parents' educational attainment. In addition, it sought to describe the effectiveness of Audio-video-initiated Initiated Presentation Innovation for primary grade pupils in terms of letter sounding, letter recognition, and word recognition. Moreover, it also sought to describe the level of reading performance of pupils in the primary grades. Furthermore, it also determined the difference in study and reading performance when grouped according to profile. On the other hand, the correlational part focused on the relationship between reading performance and the impact of Audio-video-initiated Initiated Presentation Innovation for primary-grade learners. This method of research involved the collection of data to test the hypotheses or answer questions concerning the current status of the subject under study.

Respondents

The primary grade pupils enrolled in the 2023–2024 academic year at Sagasa Elementary School, Barangay Sagasa, Bago City, Negros Occidental, served as the subject and respondents.

There were only 307 primary grade pupils from grades 1 to 3 who were taken by the researcher as the respondents of the study. Thus, the sample size was no longer computed.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents by Grade Level*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Male</i>	<i>Female</i>	<i>Total</i>
Grade I	43	38	81
Grade II	63	63	126
Grade III	44	56	100
Total	150	157	307

There were 307 total population of Primary-grade pupils 150 males and 157 females answered the survey, 81 pupils from Grade I 43 males and 38 females, 126 pupils from grade II 63 pupils both male and female and 100 pupils from grade 3, with 44 males and 56 females.

Instrument

This study employed a researcher-made instrument which composed of three factors:

Part I of the instrument determined the primary grade pupils' profile such as grade level, family income, and parent educational attainment. Part II of the instrument determined the effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation Innovation on primary-grade pupils such as letter sounding, letter recognition, and word formation.

Reading performance of primary grades pupils was taken as secondary data from their reading assessment during the mid-test result of CRLA school year 2023-2024.

Procedure

The following procedures were followed by the researcher in gathering the data from the respondents.

First, the researcher sent letters of communication to the superintendent, supervisor, and principal/school heads, asking for approval to conduct the study on the primary grade pupils of Sagasa Elementary School for the school year 2023-2024. Then, the researcher reproduced copies of the instrument to ensure a 1:1 ratio of the questionnaire. The researcher personally administered the questionnaire to ensure 100% retrieval. In addition, the researcher ensured the authenticity of the data and to made sure that the actual respondents responded properly to the questionnaire. The data were gathered, encoded, tabulated, and analyzed to answer the specific statements of the problem.

Data Analysis

After the data collection, the data were tallied, tabulated, and analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

Since this study was descriptive, the data were treated using the following statistical tools:

To answer the statement of problem 1 which states, that the profile of primary grade pupils in terms of age, sex, grade level, parent educational attainment, and monthly family income, frequency, and percentage were used.

To answer statement of the problem 2 which states, what is the effectiveness of the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) as reading innovation to primary grade pupils as a whole and when grouped in terms of letter sounding, letter recognition, and word formation, mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem 3 which states, what is the level of reading performance of primary grade pupils of Sagasa Elementary School, the mean was used.

To answer statement of the problem 4 which states, is there a significant difference in the effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation Innovation for primary grade pupils when grouped according to profile. Kruskal Wallis and Mann Whitney were used.

To answer statement of the problem 5 which states, is there a significant relationship between the effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation Innovation for primary grade pupils and their reading performance, the Gamma Coefficient was used.

To determine the enhancement plan to be formulated the researcher prepared a matrix with the procedures for the intervention.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered, its analyses, and interpretations based on the findings of the study.

Profile of Primary Grade Pupils

Table 2 below presents the profile of primary grade pupils in terms of age, sex, grade level, parents' educational attainment, and family income.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution of the Profile of Primary Grade Pupils*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	6 years old	30	9.77
	7 years old	127	41.37
	8 years old	95	30.94
	9 years old	55	17.92
	Total	307	100.00
Sex	Male	150	48.86
	Female	157	51.14
	Total	307	100.00
Grade Level	Grade 1	81	26.40
	Grade 2	126	41.00
	Grade 3	100	32.60
	Total	307	100.00
Parent's Educational Attainment	Elementary Level	5	1.63
	High School Level	218	71.01
	College Level	84	27.36
	Total	307	100.00
Family Income	Below P5,000	176	57.33
	P5,000-P10,000	62	20.20
	P10,001-P20,000	33	10.75
	P20,001 and above	36	11.73
	Total	307	100.00

Table 2 shows that out of 307 pupils in the primary grades, in terms of age, one hundred twenty-seven or 41.37 percent are 7 years old, followed by ninety-five or 30.94 percent are eight years old, fifty-five or 17.92 percent are nine years old, and thirty or 9.77 percent are 6 years old.

In terms of sex, one hundred fifty-seven or 51.14 percent are female, and one hundred fifty or 48.86 percent are male.

In terms of grade level, 26.4 percent are in grade 1 with a total of 81 pupils, 41.1 percent in grade 2 with 126 pupils and 32.5 percent with 100 pupils are in grade 3.

In terms of parent's educational attainment, two hundred eighteen or 71.01 percent are high school level, 84 or 27.36 percent are college level, and five or 1.63 are elementary level.

In terms of family income, one hundred seventy-six or 57.33 have an average family monthly income of below Php5000, sixty-two or

20.70 percent have Php5000-Php10,000, thirty-six or 11.73 percent have Php 20,000 and above and thirty-three or 10.75 percent have an average family monthly income of Php 10,001-20,000.

According to the Philippine Statistics Authority, nearly one in five Filipinos lives below the poverty line, but the real number may be much higher. According to the latest official data released by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), more Filipinos are poorer today than in 2018. Citing the Household Income and Expenditure Survey, the PSA said that the country had 19.99 million people living below the poverty line. This represents 18.9 million people, 1 percent of the population. In 2018, there were 17.67 million poor Filipinos. At the same time, the number of "food poor" increased by 1 percent, 0.1 million. The PSA also reported an unemployment rate of 7.8 percent.

The poverty situation could be worse because the PSA survey was conducted in 2021 and its poverty line is considered unrealistic by other experts. Converted to US dollars, one person in a family of five needs to earn only \$1.41 a day to survive and meet their daily food needs, according to the Philippine government.

Effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated (AVIP) Innovation Presentation to Primary Grade Pupils When Taken as a Whole and In Terms of Letter Sounding, Letter Recognition, and Word Formation

The table below presents the effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) innovation of primary grade pupils in terms of letter sounding, letter recognition, and word formation.

Table 3. *Effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation to Primary Grade Pupils When Taken as a Whole and in terms of Letter Sounding, Letter Recognition, and Word Formation*

<i>Effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Letter Sounding	4.51	High
Letter Recognition	4.53	High
Word Formation	4.51	High
As a Whole	4.52	High

Based on the data shown in Table 2, it indicates that the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation has a high effectiveness on primary-grade pupils in terms of letter recognition, letter sounding, and word formation which gained a mean of 4.53, 4.51, and 4.51 respectively. As a whole, the effectiveness of the innovation is high, as specified by the overall mean of 4.52.

The above results imply that the AVIP innovation was effective in helping students learn skills in letter pronunciation, letter recognition, and word formation. This highlights the importance of computer programs and related technologies in developing reading fluency and helping to expand vocabulary, which allows students to understand the meaning of words. In the study by Helmer et al. (2022), the authors indicated that technological tools, ranging from online learning platforms to interactive applications and digital books, provided unique opportunities to personalize and enrich the reading learning experience (Helmer et al., 2022). These technologies not only allow students to access a wide range of textual resources but also provide interactive support that can be adapted to different skill levels and learning styles. However, the effectiveness of these tools to improve reading comprehension is still under scrutiny, especially in a context where many students may have had significant interruptions in their school due to tests and distance learning (Méndez and López, 2021). It is also essential to study how technological tools can be better used to complement, instead of replacing traditional education interactions (Martín, 2023).

Level of Reading Performance of Primary Grade Pupils

Table 4 presents the level of reading performance of primary-grade pupils.

Table 4. *Level of Reading Performance of Primary Grade Pupils*

<i>Level of Reading Performance</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Grade Ready	275		
Light Refresher	32		
Moderate Refresher	0	17.63	Grade Ready
Full Refresher	0		
Total	307		

Table 4 displays the reading performance of pupils in the primary grades. Out of 307 primary-grade pupils, 275 of them are grade ready, and 32 are light refreshers, whereas none of the pupils fall under moderate refresher and full refresher. Overall, the primary-grade students' reading performance obtains a mean of 17.63, interpreted as grade-ready.

The findings above indicate that out of 307 primary grade pupils assessed in reading, 275 or 89% of them were all grade ready. This must have been achieved because of the introduction of the Audio-Visual Initiated Presentation (AVIP) innovation created by the researcher herself and utilized in teaching reading to the pupils.

The above results complement the results of a high-quality study conducted by Arabiana et al. (2020), who explored the use of cartoons

and their effects on four literacy skills: vocabulary, oral vocabulary and pronunciation, spelling, and comprehension skills. This study was conducted among six second-grade students in a public school in the Philippines. Pretest and post-test showed that multiple exposures to the cartoon resulted in incidental literacy learning in all four related domains; that is to say, the students learned vocabulary and spelling skills, which facilitated their understanding. Since there was no comparison group, and given the very small sample size and the lack of other data in this area, no generalizations can be made about the overall effectiveness of cartoons. However, this study found that literacy acquisition works holistically and that improvement in one subskill can lead to improvement in other literacy skills. This supports the idea suggested in other studies that educational technology interventions should be integrated into a broader holistic literacy program (Schling & Winters, 2018).

Castillo and Wagner (2019) studied the effectiveness of the Bridges to the Future Initiative (BFI) multimedia program in rural South Africa. This reading program was also designed with many of the features discussed in the previous summary as effective, such as being interactive, culturally appropriate, phonics-based, and connected to the existing reading program.

Difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Age

Table 5 that follows presents the difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to age.

Table 5. *Difference in the AVIP-assisted Reading Innovation According to Age*

Age	<i>f</i>	Mean Rank
6 years old	30	147.58
7 years old	127	153.27
8 years old	95	149.34
9 years old	55	167.23
Total	307	

Computed value (*H*): 1.66

p-value: 0.646

Decision: Accept *H*₀

Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The computed value according to the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, is 1.66, as shown in Table 4. It is evident from a comparison that the *p*-value of 0.646 is higher than the significance level of 0.05, leading to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the AVIP-assisted reading innovation according to age.

It implies that reading levels are influenced more by individual ability, practice, and exposure to language than by age alone. While age is frequently related to developmental stages, it is not an accurate indicator of reading ability. Several factors influence a person's reading level, including educational opportunities, access to reading resources, motivation, and specialized teaching.

For example, younger readers who receive constant support and are exposed to engaging texts can surpass the reading level of older readers who lack the same opportunities. Adults or older students who have had little exposure to reading or have had their education disrupted may have inadequate reading levels, regardless of their age.

Research shows that reading is a skill that can be developed at any age with proper strategies and resources (Zahoor-ul-Haq, Bushra Ahmad Khurram and Arshad Khan Bangash).

Difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Sex

The table shows the difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to sex.

Table 6. *Difference in the AVIP-assisted Reading Innovation According to Sex*

Sex	<i>f</i>	Mean Rank
Male	150	137.80
Female	157	169.48
Total	307	

Computed value (*U*): 9345.00

p-value: 0.002

Decision: Reject *H*₀

Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that using the Mann-Whitney U Test, the computed value (*U*) is 9345.00, and the *p*-value of 0.002 can be compared with the result that it is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This indicates that it is evident that there is a gender difference in reading literacy because females' achievement and enjoyment were far higher than males. Chunjin (2020) also found significant gender differences in students' reading literacy performance in four Chinese provinces and municipalities by analyzing PISA 2018 data, but the effects were not as significant as other factors noted: small gender differences in reading ability but large gender differences in attention to and attitudes toward reading, as well as irregular reading habits.

Reading activities that encourage classroom participation do not always have positive benefits for pupils (Cooper et al., 2018a).

Individual attitudes and emotional states influence how comfortable students are in participation-based classrooms (Cohen et al. 2019). For example, self-efficacy and a sense of social belonging have been linked to enhanced student participation, particularly in reading. Understanding student mood can help contextualize the outcomes of participating in active-learning sessions.

Actions are focused on gender identification and its effects on pupils' reading performance in the classroom. Men, for example, seem to have stronger scientific self-efficacy than women, whereas women tend to place a higher value on gender identity. These distinctions may help explain gender discrepancies in classroom reading activities. One of the few studies that assessed student engagement discovered that women participated less than expected across classes. Women made up 60% of the students in the courses on average, yet their voices were only heard 40% of the time in answer to teacher inquiries.

Recently, Ballen et al. (2019) showed that equal gender participation occurred in STEM courses at six institutions when class sizes were smaller and instructors used different teaching styles. Other studies have shown that there are significant differences in participation between men and women in different disciplines (Ballen et al., 2018; Neill et al., 2018) and at different levels of academic development (e.g., in workshops and conferences; Carter et al., 2018). Exploring the individual experiences of college students in the classroom is the first step toward creating equitable learning environments for all students.

Difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Grade Level

The table shows the difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to grade level.

Table 7. *Difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Grade Level*

Grade Level	f	Mean Rank
Grade 1	81	137.23
Grade 2	126	152.77
Grade 3	100	169.14
Total	307	

Computed value (H): 5.87
 p-value: 0.053
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the data in Table 7, the computed value (H) and p-value using the Kruskal Wallis H test are 5.87 and 0.053, respectively. Since the p-value of 0.053 is higher than the 0.05 level significance, thus the null hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is no significant difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation when classified according to age. It can also be noted that grade levels do not greatly influence the reading proficiency of primary-grade learners.

Difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Parents' Educational Attainment

Table 7 presents the difference in the AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to parents' educational attainment.

Table 7. *The Difference in the AVIP-assisted Reading Innovation According to Parents' Educational Attainment*

Parent's Educational Attainment	f	Mean Rank
Elementary Level	5	145.80
High School Level	218	150.69
College Level	84	163.07
Total	307	

Computed value (H): 1.23
 p-value: 0.540
 Decision: Accept Ho
 Interpretation: Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table shows that the computed value (H) is 1.23. The p-value of 0.540 indicates that it is above the 0.05 level of significance, thus the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore, there is no significant difference in AVIP-assisted reading innovation based on parent's educational attainment.

The result of this study is in contrast with the findings of Melencion and Alferéz (2023) concluded that the higher the family income, the better the children's reading skills, and vice versa. Family involvement has an impact on a child's academic success. There was a significant relationship between reading achievement and the demographic profile related to the highest level of parental education. The educational level of the parents influenced the child's reading ability because the higher education they had, the more knowledge they could impart, especially in teaching reading. It was also concluded that the language spoken at home can affect the child's reading, such as diction, pronunciation, and the difficulty in pronouncing the word, especially when it is new for them. On the other hand, parental education can also influence the child's reading by encouraging the use of positive parenting practices, such as the use of positive language, scheduling discipline, and helping to teach good reading habits. It also encourages caring behavior and increases parents' understanding of child development and communication styles.

Difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Family Income

Table 9 presents the difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to family income.

Table 9. *Difference in AVIP-assisted Reading Innovation According to Family Income*

Family Income	f	Mean Rank
Below P5,000	176	139.76
P5,000-P10,000	62	165.25
P10,001-P20,000	33	196.91
P20,001 and above	36	164.93
Total	307	

Computed value (H): 13.890
 p-value: 0.003
 Decision: Reject Ho
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Kruskal-Wallis H Test, the table illustrates that the computed value (H) is 13.890, and a p-value of 0.003 indicates that it is less than the 0.05 level of significance leading to the null hypothesis being rejected. This indicates a significant difference in AVIP-assisted reading innovation according to monthly family income.

Comparison of the Difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Family Income

The table below shows the comparison of the difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation according to family income.

Table 10. *Pairwise Comparison of the Difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation According to Family Income*

Comparison	Computed Value	p-value	Interpretation
Below P5,000 vs. P20,001 and above	-25.18	0.718	Not Significant
Below P5,000 vs. P5,000-P10,000	-25.49	0.306	Not Significant
Below P5,000 vs. P10,001 -P20,000	-57.15	0.004	Significant
P20,001 and above vs. P5,000-P10,000	0.32	1.000	Not Significant
P20,001 and above vs. P10,001-P20,000	31.98	0.801	Not Significant
P5,000-P10,000 vs. P10,001-P20,000	-31.66	0.580	Not Significant

The table reveals the pairwise comparison of the difference in AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation when grouped according to family income. Family income below P5,000 versus P20,001 and above gained a computed value of -25.18 and a p-value of 0.718 interpreted as not significant, and below P5,000 vs. P5,000 - P10,000 gained a computed value of -25.49 and a p-value of 0.306 interpreted as not significant, while below P5,000 vs. P10,001 - P20,000 is interpreted as significant with a computed value of -57.15 and a p-value of 0.004. On the other hand, P20,001 and above vs. P5,000-P10,000 obtained a computed value of 0.32 and a p-value of 1.000 interpreted as not significant, P20,001 and above vs. P10,001-P20,000 obtained a computed value of 31.98 and a p-value of 0.801 interpreted as not significant, and P5,000-P10,000 vs. P10,001-P20,000 obtained a computed value of -31.66 and a p-value of 0.580 interpreted as not significant. This suggests that primary-grade pupils with low to middle family income require more assistance in reading using the stated innovation.

Children from families with low incomes frequently have inadequate pre-academic skills, less interaction with learning resources, and less involvement by parents. This article evaluates some of the studies that examined how poverty impacts reading success in children's early years. The higher the level of poverty, the less likely students are to attain acceptable reading levels.

Relationship between the Level of AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation and the Level of Reading Performance of Pupils

The succeeding table presents the relationship between the level of AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation and the level of reading performance of pupils.

Table 11. *Relationship between the Level of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Assisted Reading Innovation and the Level of Reading Performance of Pupils*

Level of AVIP-Assisted Reading Innovation	Level of Reading Performance				Total
	Grade Ready	Light Refresher	Moderate Refresher	Full Refresher	
Very High	254	18	0	0	272
High	21	14	0	0	35
Moderate	0	0	0	0	0
Low	0	0	0	0	0
Very Low	0	0	0	0	0
Total	275	32	0	0	307

Computed value (G): 0.81
 p-value: <0.001
 Decision: Reject Ho
 Interpretation: Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Using the Gamma Coefficient, the table shows that the computed value is 0.81, and the p-value of 0.735 indicates that it is above the

0.05 level of significance. Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that there is a significant relationship between the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation and primary school students' reading proficiency. This also implies that the reading performance of the pupils is greatly influenced by the reading innovation with the aid of technological devices.

The use of technological advances can affect the academic performance of students, leading to lower grades (Cao et al., 2018) or addiction (Daz et al., 2019). According to Nuñez, Segundo, Jérez, Rivera, and Espinosa (2018), the academic success of students is influenced by personal and social factors. Taking a new perspective, this study suggests that early adoption and regular use of digital devices and the Internet are detrimental, as they are associated with poor academic performance. As a result, it can be concluded that there is a relationship, even negative, between the initial adoption of the Internet and digital devices and PISA test performance. Hu et al. (2018) found that students in countries with higher levels of reading technology innovations were more likely to do better academically. However, access to and use of ICT at the national level is not correlated with students' reading skills after acquiring digital skills. Therefore, the integration of technology in the curriculum and overcoming the digital divide can be defined by the basic skills needed to do it in a digital context, rather than the availability of ICT.

The results show that the educational use of technological innovation in classroom reading activities has an impact on the educational acceptance of the tools, unlike individual use without educational support. However, since teachers tend to use technological innovation for a limited number of teaching practices that do not significantly modify traditional teaching methods, an increase in the frequency of technology use does not seem to bring any tangible benefits to learning. It can also be harmful. The negative relationship between students' academic use of technological innovation, both in school and outside of school, and their learning outcomes may indicate that ICT is not being used appropriately to enhance learning. On the other hand, students' interest, competence, and autonomy in the use of technology have shown varying degrees of positive correlation with their academic performance in mathematics, reading, and science, while the use of ICT for social interaction showed negative correlations with academic performance in all three subjects. Finally, "the amount of ICT use can advance student learning only if the quality of technology use is ensured" (Hu et al., 2018).

Conclusions

Based on the above findings, the following conclusions are drawn:

Most of the respondents are 7 years old, female, in Grade 2, parents attained high school level, and family income of below Php 5,000.

The effectiveness of Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation is high.

The level of reading performance of primary-grade pupils is grade ready.

There is no significant difference in the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation according to age, grade level, and parents' educational attainment. However, there is a significant difference in the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation in terms of sex and family income.

There is a significant relationship between the Audio-Video Initiated Presentation (AVIP) Innovation and the reading performance of primary-grade pupils.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made to:

School's Education Superintendent may typically involve several key actions and strategies designed to enhance literacy outcomes. He/she creates programs that will enhance the reading performance of pupils at the school level.

The chief supervisor may create programs with specific budget allocations for the reading development of students at all grade levels.

The education program supervisor may assist school heads in establishing, implementing, and facilitating programs and activities for the improvement of primary-grade pupil's reading performance.

The school heads may include in the in-service training of teachers the techniques and new strategies in teaching literacy among students and provide technical assistance to struggling readers. He/she may also encourage reading innovations/interventions to enhance the reading performance of pupils.

Teachers may do the early identification and assessment for pupils. Use regular screening tools to identify students who are at risk of reading difficulties early in the school year. Continuously monitor students' reading progress to adjust interventions as needed. He/she will choose reading materials that match students' interests and reading levels to keep them engaged and motivated.

Parents may encourage their children to read and they will help them to follow up reading at home. Parents also may monitor the progress of their child in terms of reading.

It is recommended that present and future researchers should conduct a more comprehensive study about the effectiveness of adaptive learning platforms that tailor reading instruction to individual students' needs, and how these tools can be optimized for various learning environments.

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